

POTASSIUM PERSULPHATE AS A VOLUMETRIC REAGENT. PART I. THE IODINE MONOCHLORIDE METHOD

BY BALWANT SINGH AND NARINDER SINGH AHUJA

Potassium persulphate has been used as a volumetric reagent for the direct determination of arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, ferrous ammonium sulphate, ferrous ethylenediamine sulphate, mercurous chloride, potassium thiocyanate, hydrazine sulphate and hydroquinone in hydrochloric acid medium at room temperature, using iodine monochloride as a catalyst and pre-oxidiser. Chloroform has been used as an indicator. It is coloured violet owing to the liberation of iodine during the titration and becomes very pale yellow at the end-point due to the formation of iodine monochloride. Normality of the solution with respect to hydrochloric acid is kept between 6.0N and 7.5N in these redox titrations.

Marshall (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1900, 23, 163) found an aqueous solution of persulphuric acid ($H_2S_2O_8$) to be a strong oxidising agent and oxidised chromium to chromic acid and ammonia to nitrogen only in presence of a silver salt as a catalyst. Dittrich and Bollenbach (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 747) showed that chloride, bromide and iodide ions could be oxidised to chlorate, bromate and iodate respectively by persulphuric acid, catalysed by silver ions. Eckardt (*Chem. News*, 1900, 81, 30) used persulphate for the quantitative oxidation of Fe^{II} to Fe^{III} at 80°. Kempf (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3963) observed that oxalic acid was rapidly and quantitatively oxidised by persulphate in presence of a small amount of silver salt. Willard and Young (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1379) determined Ce^{III} by oxidation with persulphate in presence of silver nitrate as catalyst, followed by electrometric titration of the excess persulphate with ferrous sulphate, potassium iodide or sodium nitrite. King and Jette (*ibid.*, 1930, 52, 608) recommended persulphate as an oxidimetric standard in iodometry. Yost and Claussen (*ibid.*, 1931, 53, 3349) oxidised vanadyl ion to vanadic acid with persulphate, using silver ion as catalyst. Dehn and Ballard (*ibid.*, 1932, 54, 4264) used alkaline persulphate as an analytical reagent for the oxidation of cyanide, ferrocyanide, nitroprusside and thiocyanates to cyanic acid. Another volumetric method was suggested by Bright and Larrabee (*Bur. Standards J. Res.*, 1929, 3, 573) and modified by Sandell *et al.* (*Ind. Eng. Chem.; Anal. Ed.*, 1935, 7, 256) in which Mn^{II} was oxidised to permanganate by persulphate in hot acid solution in presence of silver ions; permanganate so formed was estimated by sodium arsenite or by a mixture of sodium arsenite and sodium nitrite.

Of the several reductometric methods for the volumetric determination of persulphate, the iodometric and ferrometric methods are found to be most practicable from the points of view of rate of reaction, accuracy and simplicity. All the volumetric methods, proposed so far, are indirect and involve the oxidation of certain reducing agents with persulphate.

In the present study, potassium persulphate has been used as a volumetric reagent for the direct visual titrations of arsenious oxide, tartar emetic, ferrous ammonium sulphate, ferrous ethylenediamine sulphate, mercurous chloride, potassium thiocyanate, hydrazine sulphate and hydroquinone in hydrochloric acid medium at room temperature.

Iodine monochloride has been used as a catalyst and pre-oxidiser in these redox titrations. The oxidation by potassium persulphate proceeds according to the following reactions :

EXPERIMENTAL

A known amount of each substance was transferred to a conical flask and about 10 c.c. of water, sufficient HCl to keep the normality of solution between 6.0N and 7.5N, 5 c.c. of 0.02M iodine monochloride and 5 c.c. of chloroform were added. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and titrated with 0.05M potassium persulphate. The reagent was added from a burette until the solution, which was coloured with iodine, became pale yellow and the chloroform layer acquired a purple colour due to iodine. The flask was stoppered and vigorously shaken during the titration. Addition of small volumes of the persulphate solution was continued, shaking vigorously after each addition, till the chloroform layer was faintly violet. The persulphate was then added dropwise, with shaking after the addition of each drop, till the chloroform layer became very pale yellow. The end-point was very sharp. Several titrations were performed in each case. From the volume of potassium persulphate solution used, corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of the substance was calculated. Some typical results, recorded in Table I, show that the substances listed above can be determined by direct titration with potassium persulphate.

TABLE I
Titration with 0.05M-K₂S₂O₈.

	Taken.	Found.
As ₂ O ₃	0.0495 g. 0.1246	0.0495 g. 0.1244
K(SbO).C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ .0.5H ₂ O	0.0835 0.2093	0.0835 0.2091
FeSO ₄ .(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ .6H ₂ O	0.2353 1.0195	0.2353 1.0194
FeSO ₄ .(CH ₃ .NH ₂) ₂ SO ₄ .4H ₂ O	0.2088 0.9761	0.2088 0.9762
Hg ₂ Cl ₂	0.1882 0.6023	0.1880 0.6018
KCNS	0.0167 0.0365	0.0167 0.0364
NH ₂ .NH ₂ .H ₂ SO ₄	0.0295 0.0780	0.0295 0.0780
C ₆ H ₄ (OH) ₂	0.0486 0.1377	0.0484 0.1374

All chemicals used in this investigation were of guaranteed purity. Ferrous ethylenediamine sulphate was prepared by the method of Caraway and Oesper (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1947, 24, 235). Potassium persulphate solution (0.05M) was standardised by the iodometric method of Gopala Rao *et al.* (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1945, 11, 331 ; 1946, 12, 277).

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY COLLEGE,
HOSEHARPUR.

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